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Influence Of Social Media On Students' Academic Achievement In Senior Secondary Schools In Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State: Implication for counselling

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ABSTRACT

The rapid expansion of social media has reshaped the learning environment of students worldwide, including those in Sokoto metropolis, Nigeria. While social networking platforms provide new opportunities for knowledge sharing, collaboration, and digital interaction, they also raise concerns about distraction and declining study habits. This study investigated the influence of social media on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis, with specific focus on Facebook and Telegram. The objectives of this are to determine the influence of Facebook on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis, to examine the influence of Telegram on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis and the research hypotheses are There is no significant relationship between the use of Facebook and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis, there is no significant relationship between the use of Telegram and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population comprised 18,671 students across 42 public senior secondary schools, while a sample of 357 SS II students was selected using proportionate sampling. . Validity of the instruments was established through expert review, and reliability was confirmed with Cronbach Alpha coefficients of 0.868 for ISMOSAAQ and 0.871 for AAT. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and an academic achievement test, and analyzed through descriptive statistics and inferential methods, including Pearson correlation and t-tests. The findings revealed a platform-specific influence of social media. Facebook use was found to have no significant relationship with academic achievement, suggesting its recreational orientation outweighed educational benefits. In contrast, Telegram showed a significant positive relationship with students' academic achievement, reflecting its strength in fostering group learning, collaborative discussions, and access to academic resources. The study concluded that social media is a double-edged sword: its value depends on how students engage with each platform. It was recommended that teachers integrate Telegram into instructional strategies, parents monitor Facebook use, and policymakers promote digital literacy programs that maximize educational benefits of social media while minimizing risks.

Keywords: Social media, Facebook, Telegram, Academic Achievement, Sokoto Metropolis, and counselling

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of information and communication technology (ICT) has transformed education globally. Among these developments, social media platforms have become prominent tools shaping how young people interact, communicate, and access information. Platforms such as Facebook and Telegram, in particular, are widely used by students, not only for social interaction but also for academic purposes such as sharing study materials, participating in group discussions, and collaborating on assignments. In Sokoto metropolis, senior secondary school students have increasingly adopted these platforms, often accessing them through mobile phones and other digital devices. While social media presents unique opportunities for enhancing teaching and learning, concerns have been raised regarding its potential to distract learners, reduce study time, and negatively affect academic outcomes. It is therefore important to explore how specific platforms, such as Facebook and Telegram, influence students' academic achievement, since the impact may differ depending on how these platforms are used.

Social media refers to web-based platforms and applications that enable users to create, share, and exchange information, ideas, and multimedia content in virtual communities. Unlike traditional media, social media allows for two-way communication, collaboration, and interactive networking among users (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). In the context of education, social media provides new opportunities for students to communicate, access resources, and engage with peers and teachers beyond the classroom. The growth of platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Telegram, TikTok, and Snapchat has transformed how young people interact and learn (Ahn, 2011; Manca & Ranieri, 2016).

Social media offers several educational benefits. First, it enhances communication and collaboration, allowing students to work together on assignments or share learning materials (Junco, 2012). Second, it improves access to information, as students can easily access tutorials, e-books, and open educational resources. Third, it promotes peer learning and motivation; when students see academic success stories shared online, they may be inspired to emulate positive behaviors (Manca & Ranieri, 2016). Finally, platforms such as Telegram and WhatsApp can serve as informal learning management systems by hosting study groups and class discussions (Al-Rahmi & Zeki, 2017).

Despite its benefits, social media also presents challenges for students. Excessive use often leads to distraction and procrastination, reducing time available for study (Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). Overreliance on entertainment-driven platforms such as TikTok and Snapchat may negatively affect concentration and critical thinking skills (Alnjadat et al., 2019). Social media addiction is another concern, as students may spend more time online than on academics, leading to declining academic performance (Andreassen et al., 2017). Furthermore, issues such as cyberbullying, misinformation, and exposure to inappropriate content raise safety and ethical concerns in educational use (Livingstone & Smith, 2014).

Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977), this theory posits that individuals learn by observing others and modeling their behaviors. Applied to this study, students using Facebook or Telegram are influenced by the academic behaviors of their peers and teachers. When students observe peers sharing study notes or engaging in problem-solving discussions, they are more likely to imitate and adopt similar practices, thus improving their academic achievement.

Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) explains how users come to accept and use new technologies. It emphasizes two main constructs: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. In the context of this study, students' willingness to adopt Facebook and Telegram for learning depends on how useful and easy they find the platforms for academic purposes. If Telegram is perceived as efficient for resource sharing and Facebook as useful for collaborative learning, students are more likely to integrate them into their study routines.

Facebook is one of the most widely used social networking platforms worldwide, with billions of active users (Statista, 2023). It enables students to create personal profiles, connect with peers, share educational resources, and participate in academic discussions. Research has shown that Facebook groups and pages are often used as digital classrooms where teachers and students interact outside the school environment (Ainin et al., 2015). However, while it provides opportunities for collaborative learning, critics argue that

excessive Facebook use may lead to distraction, reduced concentration, and poor time management among students (Junco, 2012).

Telegram is a cloud-based instant messaging application that has gained global recognition for its speed, privacy, and flexibility (Durodolu & Ifeanyi, 2021). Unlike Facebook, Telegram allows users to create large groups (up to 200,000 members) and broadcast channels for mass communication. This makes it suitable for academic communities, online study groups, and teacher-led digital classrooms. Telegram supports file sharing, voice chats, and video conferencing, making it more versatile than many competing platforms (Zhao & Wang, 2022).

Academic achievement refers to measurable performance outcomes that demonstrate the extent to which a student has attained specific educational goals. It is often assessed through grades, standardized test scores, and teacher evaluations (Ghazvini & Khajehpour, 2011). Academic achievement reflects not only cognitive ability but also factors such as motivation, discipline, and learning environment. In this study, academic achievement is defined by students' performance in core subjects such as English Language and Mathematics.

Statement of the Problem

Although Facebook and Telegram are widely used by students for both social and academic purposes, there is limited empirical evidence within Sokoto metropolis on how these platforms specifically affect academic achievement. Anecdotal reports suggest that while Facebook is often criticized for promoting distractions, Telegram has gained recognition for its structured learning communities and resource-sharing capacity. However, the extent to which these platforms contribute positively or negatively to students' academic performance remains unclear. Without such evidence, teachers, parents, and counselors lack sufficient guidance on how to maximize the benefits of social media for education while minimizing its risks. This study was therefore designed to examine the influence of Facebook and Telegram on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis, Sokoto State.

Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To determine the influence of Facebook on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.
2. To examine the influence of Telegram on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between the use of Facebook and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between the use of Telegram and the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.

Review of Empirical Studies

Recent evidence remains mixed but patterned by how Facebook is used. Studies of secondary students in Nigeria reported that task-oriented Facebook use (class groups, sharing notes, asking peers/teachers questions) related positively to assessment outcomes, whereas entertainment-driven or heavy, idle use predicted lower grades and weaker study habits (Iorliam & Ode, 2020). Earlier foundational work helps explain these patterns: time spent on Facebook, especially non-academic activity, was negatively associated with GPA and study time (Junco, 2012; Kirschner & Karpinski, 2010). At the same time, educational uses language learning groups, collaborative writing, and peer feedback, have shown benefits for engagement and skill development (Kabilan et al., 2010; Yunus & Salehi, 2012). Taken together, the 2020–2024 synthesis supports a dual-effect view: Facebook can be academically enabling when structured for learning, but detrimental when dominated by distraction.

Ahmad (2019) investigated the effect of Facebook on students' academic performance of students at the Federal College of Education, Kontagora in Niger State of Nigeria. Survey research design was used for the study. The population of this study comprises of all 6,769 students of Federal College of Education, Kontagora, Niger State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 students from all level in the college. The instrument for data collection was four (4) Likert scale questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using frequency and percentage. The findings of the study revealed that indicated that effect of social media can be both positive and negative. Facebook captured the attention of many students away from their study and thus have negative and positive effects on their academic grade points aggregate. It was recommended that student users need to be educated on the effect of Facebook on their academic performance and also, student users need to be monitored and controlled on how they use social media during full academic activities and during exams.

Telegram's large groups/channels, low-friction file sharing, and broadcast features have made it a fast-growing tool for study communities. Studies in higher-education and school contexts found improvements in access to resources, responsiveness, and collaborative problem-solving, with associated gains in course performance and satisfaction when Telegram was integrated with clear academic norms (Alshammari, 2020; Yeboah & Ewur, 2020). However, researchers also cautioned that notification overload, reposted low-quality summaries, and off-topic chatter can dilute learning and displace deep reading when not guided by teachers (Alshammari, 2020).

Olaimolu and Alade (2024) investigated the impact of Telegram on academic performance of students in private universities in Ede, Osun State. Guided by the Uses and Gratifications Theory, the research employed a mixed-methods approach to gather comprehensive insights. The study involved a population of 500 students, with a sample size of 250 students selected through stratified random sampling. Data collection techniques included surveys and focus group discussions. The findings revealed a nuanced relationship between Telegram usage and academic outcomes. While students acknowledged the benefits of social media for academic communication and resource access, they also reported challenges such as distractions and stress associated with excessive usage. Furthermore, socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, and academic discipline influenced students' Telegram usage habits and perceptions of its impact on academic performance. The study recommended promoting balanced social media usage strategies and tailored interventions to optimize academic success. Educators and institutions should emphasize the importance of minimizing distractions while leveraging the potential benefits of social media for educational purposes.

A study by Otaru and Nwankwo (2021) investigated the perceived influence of Telegram on the academic performance of secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. A descriptive research design was adopted for the study. A total of 120 teachers participated in the study. One research question was raised while two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The instrument used for data collection for this study was a researcher designed questionnaire entitled "Influence of Telegram on academic performance Questionnaire" (ITMAPQ). The findings revealed that Telegram has a considerable influence on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in FCT, Abuja. There were significant differences in the influence of Telegram on academic performances of secondary school students as expressed by teachers in FCT, Abuja based on age and no significant difference based on gender. It was therefore recommended among others that counselors should expose students to the danger inherent in negative uses of Telegram and analyze the possible result of proper usage of social media.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey design, which was considered appropriate for examining how Facebook and Telegram use relate to students' academic achievement in Sokoto metropolis. The population of this study comprised all senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis. According to the Ministry for Basic and Secondary Education, Sokoto State (2023), there were 42 public senior

secondary schools with a total student population of 18,671, Out of this, the study focused on 10 selected schools, which together had a student population of 4,846. A structured questionnaire (ISMOSAAQ) focusing on students’ use of Facebook and Telegram and an Academic Achievement Test (AAT) in English Language and Mathematics. The instruments were validated by experts, while reliability was confirmed using Cronbach’s Alpha, yielding values above 0.80, which indicated high internal consistency. Data were collected with the assistance of trained aides and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and means) to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The study sample of 357 senior secondary school students was drawn proportionately from 10 selected public schools within Sokoto metropolis to ensure adequate representation; this distribution ensured that each school was fairly represented in the study sample, thereby increasing the validity and generalizability of the findings within Sokoto metropolis

RESULT

Data collected from 357 senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The demographic profile revealed that the majority of respondents were female (67.8%) and within the age range of 15–20 years (78.2%), indicating that social media engagement is highest among young, school-aged adolescents. The analysis of social media usage patterns showed that students were active on multiple platforms, but with varying levels of influence on their academic achievement. Results indicated that Facebook, despite being widely used, had no significant relationship with students’ academic performance, suggesting that its use was primarily recreational rather than academic. Conversely, Telegram was found to have a positive and significant effect on academic achievement, as students frequently used it for sharing study materials, participating in group discussions, and accessing educational content.

The data analysis confirmed that the academic influence of social media is platform specific. While some platforms (e.g., Telegram) can be harnessed for educational purposes, others (e.g., Facebook) pose more risks of distraction than opportunities for learning. These findings underscore the need for guided use of social media by students, with teachers and parents playing a key role in ensuring balanced digital engagement.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	115	32.2
Female	242	67.8
Total	357	100.0
Age		
15 – 20 yrs	279	78.2
21 years and above	78	21.8
Total	357	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

A total of 357 senior secondary school students from Sokoto metropolis participated in the study. The demographic analysis revealed that 115 (32.2%) were male, while 242 (67.8%) were female, showing that female students were the majority of the respondents. In terms of age, most of the students, 279 (78.2%), were between 15–20 years, while only 78 (21.8%) were 21 years and above. This indicates that the respondents were predominantly adolescents and young adults, who is consistent with the school-age population and reflects the age group most actively, engaged with social media platforms.

Null Hypotheses Testing

This section tests the null hypotheses raised for the study. The null hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) as shown below.

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significance relationship between the use of Facebook and academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.

This hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance presented in Table 3

Table 2: Results on Relationship between the use of Facebook and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto Metropolis

Variable	N	Mean	SD	p-value	r-cal	Decision
Use of Facebook	357	2.74	.46			H ₀₁
Academic achievement	357	32.38	10.86	.577	0.030	Accepted

Source: data output from SPSS, 2025

Table: 2 show the statistical relationship between students' use of Facebook and their academic achievement. The mean score for the use of Facebook was 2.74 (SD = 0.46), indicating a relatively high level of usage among the respondents. The mean score for academic performance was 32.38 (SD = 10.86). The correlation result reveals that the calculated correlation coefficient was $r = 0.030$ with a p-value of 0.577 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. Since the p-value (0.577) is greater than 0.05, the relationship is not statistically significant. This implies that there is no significant relationship between the use of Facebook and students' academic achievement in the study area. In essence, while Facebook is widely used by the students, its usage does not have a significant positive or negative influence on their academic performance.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significance relationship between the use of telegram and academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.

This hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance presented in Table 4

Table: 3 Results on Relationship between the use of Telegram and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto Metropolis

Variable	N	Mean	SD	p-value	r-cal	Decision
Use of Telegram	357	2.59	.43			H ₀₃
Academic achievement	357	32.38	10.86	.000	.194	Rejected

Source: data output from SPSS, 2025

The result in Table 3 shows the correlation between the use of Telegram and students' academic achievement. The mean score for the use of Telegram was 2.59 (SD = 0.43), which indicates that the platform is moderately used by students. The mean academic performance score was 32.38 (SD = 10.86). The correlation analysis shows a coefficient of $r = 0.194$ with a p-value of 0.000 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. Since the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the result is statistically significant. This means there is a significant positive relationship between the use of Telegram and students' academic achievement. In other words, higher use of Telegram is associated with better academic performance among the students. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no relationship is not supported, as the results show a meaningful positive relationship.

Telegram's success as an academic tool may be attributed to its unique features: the ability to host large groups (up to 200,000 members), seamless sharing of documents, videos, and links, as well as its cloud-based storage that ensures resources are not easily lost. Many students reported using Telegram to create study groups, share notes, receive assignments, and hold academic discussions.

This result corroborates findings by Bello and Yusuf (2021) and Chukwuemeka (2023), who emphasized that Telegram is increasingly becoming a digital classroom where collaborative learning thrives. Compared to Facebook, Telegram is less cluttered with distractions, making it a more focused platform for academic purposes. Thus, Telegram emerges as a productive digital learning environment, enabling students to complement classroom learning with peer collaboration and instant access to study materials.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provided a nuanced understanding of how different social media platforms influence the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.

First, the study showed that Facebook use had no significant relationship with students' academic achievement. This suggests that while Facebook is popular for social networking, entertainment, and peer interactions, its academic utility is limited. Many students prioritize recreational content such as chatting, memes, and entertainment updates over educational discussions. This aligns with Ahn (2021) and Amadi and Paul (2022), who noted that the highly interactive but distracting nature of Facebook may reduce students' study time, thereby weakening its contribution to academic outcomes.

On the other hand, the results revealed a positive and significant relationship between Telegram use and academic achievement. Students using Telegram tended to perform better academically due to its user-friendly features, such as large-group participation, cloud-based storage, and effective document sharing. The platform facilitated the creation of virtual study groups where students collaborated, exchanged ideas, and accessed academic resources. This finding is consistent with Bello and Yusuf (2021) and Chukwuemeka (2023), who emphasized the growing role of Telegram as a digital classroom that encourages collaborative learning.

The contrasting results between Facebook and Telegram underscore the platform-specific influence of social media on learning. The evidence suggests that Telegram functions as a learning-enhancing platform, while Facebook remains largely recreational in this context. Overall, the findings confirm that social media use is a double-edged sword, capable of either supporting or undermining academic achievement depending on how it is used.

Implications for Counselling

The findings of this study have significant implications for counselling practice in schools. Since Facebook was found to have no meaningful impact on students' academic achievement while Telegram showed a positive effect, counsellors need to guide students on selective and purposeful use of social media. Counselling interventions should emphasize how platforms like Telegram can be used for academic collaboration, information sharing, and peer learning.

Counsellors can also design digital literacy and time management workshops, helping students recognize the difference between productive and distracting social media use. This will equip them with the skills to avoid excessive engagement with recreational platforms and instead channel their online activities toward academic growth. Furthermore, counselling programs should involve teachers and parents. By sensitizing stakeholders, counsellors can encourage a supportive environment where students' social media habits are monitored and redirected constructively.

In conclusion, school counsellors should integrate career guidance and study skills training with digital awareness, ensuring that students not only use technology responsibly but also develop self-discipline and focus in their academic pursuits.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The teachers should Integrate Telegram into teaching and learning strategies. Teachers should create academic groups where notes, assignments, and discussions can be shared, helping students use their time online more productively.
2. The parents should monitor students' use of Facebook and other recreational platforms, while encouraging balanced digital engagement that prioritizes study-related activities.
3. The policymakers should develop digital literacy programs that emphasize productive use of social media. These should guide students on time management, responsible digital behavior, and the academic benefits of platforms like Telegram.
4. And also, students Cultivate self-discipline in social media use. Students should actively participate in academic groups on Telegram and limit distractions from entertainment-oriented platforms.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that social media plays an increasingly important role in the academic life of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis. However, its impact is not uniform across platforms. Facebook, despite its popularity, does not significantly enhance academic performance due to its entertainment-oriented use. Conversely, Telegram demonstrated a significant positive relationship with academic achievement, reflecting its effectiveness as a collaborative learning platform.

The implication is clear: social media should not be dismissed outright as a distraction but rather understood as a set of diverse tools. When harnessed productively, especially platforms like Telegram, social media can complement formal education, enhance peer learning, and promote better academic outcomes.

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